

bred at the Agricultural Research Station, Bombuwela, is a 120-day samba rice variety recommended for cultivation

in the low-country wet zone of Sri Lanka. It is resistant to blast, has tolerance for iron toxicity and is

moderately resistant to gall midge and storage pests. It has good grain quality. ■

Performance of IET7041 in nitrogen variety trial

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A field trial was conducted on a black clayey soil with high organic matter content, medium phosphorus and high potassium contents, and a pH of 7.5 during kharif (Jun-Nov) 1979 at the Regional Center, All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project, Maruteru, A. P. Six prerelease lines and two released varieties (Table 1) constituted the main plots, and four nitrogen levels were the subplots in a split-plot design with three replications. A basal applica-

Table 1. Details of entries in nitrogen variety trial, APAU, 1979 kharif.

IET no.	Designation	Cross	Maturity (days)	100-grain wt (g)	Rice type ^a
5656	RP975-109-2	Sona/RPW6-13	155	26	LB
5854	RP1017-76-1-4-3	Sona/Mahsuri	150	18	MS
6056	RP894-61-1-3-7-2	CR44-35/W12708	155	19	MS
6212	RP1064-14-2-2	RP31-49-2/Patnai 23	155	25	SB
6314	RP1045-23-2-1	RP31-49-2/LMN	160	25	SB
7041	MTU7029	Vasista/Mahsuri	155	19	MS
	Pankaj (check)		155	28	LB
	Mahsuri (check)		150	16	MS

^aLB = long, bold; SB = short, bold; MS = medium, slender.

tion of 30 kg P₂O₅ and 30 kg K₂O/ha was applied. Nitrogen was applied 50% at transplanting, 25% at 25 days after transplanting (DT), and 25% at 50 DT.

IET7041 (MTU7029), developed at APAU, yielded highest (Table 2). The optimum level of nitrogen for it was 30

kg/ha. It had the highest panicle number at all nitrogen levels.

IET7041 should be suited for good yields on soils with high organic matter at lower nitrogen inputs in kharif on the Krishna and Godavari deltas of A.P. ■

Table 2. Summary of results of nitrogen variety trial, APAU, 1979 kharif.

Nitrogen level (kg/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)							
	IET7041	IET5656	Pankaj	IET6314	IET6056	IET6212	IET5854	Mahsuri (check)
0	5.9	5.1	5.0	4.6	5.0	4.1	4.5	3.8
30	6.0	5.2	4.9	4.8	4.3	4.1	4.1	3.2
60	6.3	5.2	5.0	4.8	4.1	4.4	3.7	3.2
90	6.4	4.8	4.6	4.3	4.5	4.3	3.0	2.4

C.D. (P = 0.05) for varieties, 0.6 t/ha; for nitrogen levels, 0.3 t/ha.

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Disease resistance

Studies on false-smut disease caused by *Ustilaginoidea virens* on paddy in Karnataka, India

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False smut on paddy has occurred in Karnataka for more than 3 decades. The preliminary survey conducted for more than 5 years indicates that the disease occurs on both modern and local improved varieties throughout the state

during the kharif, particularly on varieties that are late sown and flower late (usually from November). The data collected indicate that the disease incidence on some varieties varies from less than 1% to more than 50%. The percentage of incidence has been taken on the panicle basis, irrespective of the number of smut balls formed on each panicle.

Some varieties showed less than 10% incidence: IET2885 (7.92), IET2886 (5.62), IET1789 (1.08), IR26 (0.48), IET2295 (4.33), Sona (0.77), and IET3359 (1.42). Varieties among the IRON entries of kharif 1976 that showed

more than 50% disease incidence were IR4427-315-2-3, IR4442-45-2-1, IR4722-36-1, IR5853-31, and IR2863-31-3. Among the NSN entries of kharif 1976 with more than 50% disease incidence were RP894-61-1-10-7, RP974-4-7-6-2, RP6-590-22-5-4-1, Biplat, and IR2071-588-1-1-1.

Further information indicates that the number of smut balls varies from 1 to 6/panicle; 2-4 smut balls have been observed on more than 50% of infected panicles; 1-6 smut balls have been observed on 16%, 32%, 26%, 14%, 8.20%, and 3.80% of infected panicles.

Further studies on varieties GMR-2 (IET2885) and Rasi (IET1444), which were in insecticidal trials, showed more than 30% incidence on some treatments. These varieties were late sown and flowered late. When the same varieties were early sown and thus flowered early, they were not at all infected. This indicates that the time of flowering has some influence on disease incidence. ■

Varietal resistance to tungro

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Tungro virus disease first appeared in Tanjore district, Tamil Nadu, in 1978. In the 1979 thaladi season, some devastated fields of tungro-affected paddy were plowed under. The disease appears starting in the early kuruvai season and damage becomes severe in late kuruvai, samba, and thaladi. To select tungro-resistant varieties, observations were made in 3 sets (6 entries/set) of plantings made in kuruvai (6 plantings in Jun-Jul), samba (2 plantings, Oct), and thaladi (6 plantings, Oct-Nov). Among the 18 varieties (see table), TKM9 was best for kuruvai; CR1009, C025, and AD3488 for samba; and Ponni for thaladi. ■

Sources of varietal resistance to rice tungro virus. Tamil Nadu, India.

Variety	Rice tungro virus (%)
<i>Kuruvai</i>	
ADT31	48.4
TKM9	13.8
AS3704	26.6
PL29	22.9
AD8991	48.9
AD6120	22.1
<i>Samba</i>	
C025	10.0
CO40	63.6
NLR9672	56.1
CR1009	9.5
AD7496	54.6
AD3488	15.3
<i>Thaladi</i>	
ASD15	27.8
ADT32	30.0
ADT35	19.9
IR34	16.0
Ponni	8.2
AD9408	20.8

Fake smut and bunt diseases in IRON entries

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In 1979 kharif, the natural incidence of false smut *Ustilaginoidea virens* Cke. (Takahashi) and bunt *Tilletia barclayana* Bref. (Sacc. & Syd.) diseases was observed in the International Rice Observational Nursery (IRON) trial at CRRI. The diseases occurred on 11 of 345 entries. The infected panicles and grains per panicle were counted from

randomly selected plants of each of the 11 entries (see table).

The maximum false smut infection (22%) was in CR1022; that of bunt (12%) was in B541B-PN-58-5-3-1. The maximum number of false smut-infected grains (1-6) was in CR1013.

Most of the entries flowered in late October. One week before and after flowering the maximum/minimum temperature was 33°/24° C; relative humidity was 88-95%, and sunshine hours, about 9-10. Rain fell on only 1 day during the period. The crop was irrigated when necessary. ■

Occurrence of false smut and bunt diseases in entries of the International Rice Observational Nursery at CRRI, Cuttack, Orissa, India.

Entry	Plant infection (%)	Infected grains (no./panicle)
False smut.		
CR1022 (Jagannath natural cross)	22	1-2
CR1016 (Waikoku/T90(40))	20	1-2
CR1013 (Jagannath natural cross)	16	1-6
IET6080 (RP894-15-2-1-1) CR44-35/W12708	16	1-3
IET6426, CRM9-3633-18, GEB24 mutant	8	1-4
IET6056 (RP894-61-1-3-7-2) CR44-35/W12708	4	1-2
IET6496 (R22-2-10.1) IRI/Sigadis	2	0-1
BW100 (H501/Sel. 306)	2	1-2
BW78-7 (H501/Sel. 306)	2	1-2
Bunt		
B541B-PN-58-5-3-1, Politai-I/IR1108-2	12	1-3
B2360-8-5-L-R-4-3, IR2180-2/IR2178-1	6	1-3

Records of heavy attack of bunt and false smut of rice

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Although bunt [*Tilletia barclayana* (Bref.) Sacc. & Syd. = *Neovossia horrida* (Tak.) Padwick & Khan] and false smut [*Claviceps virens* (Cke.) Sakurai ex Nakata = *Ustilaginoidea virens* (Cke.) Tak.] are widespread diseases of

rice in Assam, they are considered minor because they affect only a few grains. With the introduction of new cultivars and application of fertilizers, occurrences of the diseases are, however, on the increase. Two unusually heavy occurrences in the Rice Experimental Station at Titabar and the surrounding areas in 1964 and 1965 are reported (Table 1, 2). The information gives the average percentage of infected grains of the infected panicles only and does not

Table 1. Infected grains due to bunt and false smut (alone or combined) on infected panicles, Assam, India, 1964.

Disease	Infected panicles (no.)	Total no. of grain	Total no. of affected grain	Affected grain (%)
Bunt	19	3608	1239	34.21
False smut	7	1298	473	36.44
Bunt + false smut	2	329	188	57.14